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A Tri-Directional Examination of Parental Personality, Parenting, and Context on Adolescent Behaviors: A Replication and Extension in a New Cultural Context

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Abstract

Introduction: The aim of this study was to replicate the Tri-Directional Framework of Parent and Offspring Traits and Outcomes (TDF-POTO) in the new ground of the more traditional cultural context of Serbia. We tested the effects of: a) parental dark traits on self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting, including the moderating role of harsh contextual characteristics (low socioeconomic status and high parental adverse childhood experiences); b) parental dark traits and parenting on adolescent behavioral outcomes.

Methods: The sample included 239 parent-adolescent dyads from Serbia (68.6% mothers; 61.1% daughters; all White) with average age of 44.68 years for parents and 14.11 years for adolescents. The study was conducted in 2024 and it was cross-sectional with surveys administered to both parents and adolescents.

Results: Parental dark traits were associated with hostile, cold parenting, except for grandiose narcissism which showed a negative association with parental control. Harsh contextual characteristics moderated relationships between vulnerable narcissism and parental hostility. Only parental Machiavellianism showed significant effects on adolescent-reported parenting and behavioral outcomes. Among parenting dimensions, parental hostility showed positive associations with adolescent externalizing and internalizing behaviors and negative with prosocial behaviors, whereas parental control was negatively associated with externalizing behaviors.

Surprisingly, self-reported parental warmth was positively associated with adolescent internalizing behaviors.

Conclusions: Results support the TDF-POTO in Serbian culture but highlight some culturally specific effects of harsh contexts and associations between parenting and adolescent behavioral outcomes.

Keywords: Dark Triad; personality; parenting; adolescence; cross-cultural

1 Introduction

The Tri-Directional Framework of Parent and Offspring Traits and Outcomes (TDF-POTO; Truhan et al., 2024) highlights the necessity of considering the interconnections among parental and offspring traits, parenting, and contextual factors in influencing offspring (e.g., behavior) and parental (e.g., stress) outcomes. Based on classical theories of development including the bioecological model (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006) and developmental systems perspective (Capaldi et al., 2005), this framework applies established parent-offspring processes specifically to the study of intraindividual traits, i.e., personality. Similar approaches have been applied to the study of the developmental origins of callous-unemotional traits (e.g., Bedford et al., 2015; Flexon & Encalada, 2021). Although this framework is developed to be global, its postulations have so far only been tested via the Parents and Children Together project in the United Kingdom (PaCT; Truhan et al., 2022, 2023) and the Longitudinal Study of Australian Children (LSAC; Robson et al., 2023), more individualistic and egalitarian cultures. The question arises whether they could be confirmed in other, culturally-different societies, such as Serbia.

Serbia is a more traditional society with higher in-group collectivism and power distance and lower gender egalitarianism, which affects parent-child relationships and parenting (Mihic & Petrovic, 2009). Family is considered the cornerstone of Serbian society, with a strong emphasis on loyalty, mutual support, and interdependence among family members throughout life (Mihic & Petrovic, 2009). Children are expected to respect their parents and uphold family traditions, reflecting the cultural importance of these values. Consequently, Serbian parenting often combines authoritative and authoritarian elements, reflecting a more traditional model of parenting. While warmth and nurturing are present, there is also a strong focus on discipline, respect for authority, and adherence to traditional roles. As a result, parenting practices in Serbia may include the use of corporal punishment and the enforcement of rules and directives with limited negotiation, aiming

to discipline children (Pejović & Tošković, 2020). To test the TDF-POTO cross-culturally, we investigated the effects of parental dark personality traits, parenting behavior, and economic and parental childhood adversity risk factors on adolescent behavioral outcomes with Serbian parents and adolescents. Thus, we both replicated the study conducted in the UK (Truhan et al., 2022, 2023) and extended it to the more traditional culture of Serbia.

1.1 The Tri-Directional Framework of Parent and Offspring Traits and Outcomes

The TDF-POTO is a relatively novel approach that provides an outline for researching parent and offspring personality and outcomes while accounting for parenting behavior and context, as well as the underlying influence of genetics (Truhan et al., 2024). Meta-analytic evidence shows personality has a significant impact on parenting behavior – although this is limited to the Big Five traits (McCabe, 2014; Prinzie et al., 2009). Extending beyond the Big Five, the TDF-POTO places particular emphasis on ‘darker’ personality traits as these constructs capture psychological characteristics which typically have stronger impacts on negative or more controlling behaviors (e.g., aggression, exploitation, manipulation; Muris et al., 2017).

The TDF-POTO is named after the three interacting domains: 1) parent and offspring traits (e.g., dark traits), 2) parenting behavior (e.g., warmth), and 3) contextual factors (e.g., socioeconomic status). These domains collectively influence both parental (e.g., stress) and offspring (e.g., antisocial behaviors) outcomes. Additionally, outcomes can influence parental and offspring traits, as well as parenting behaviors, thereby shaping future traits and subsequent outcomes. Thus, the framework integrates both unidirectional effects (e.g., the impact of poverty on negative parenting or adolescent antisocial behavior) and bidirectional effects (e.g., the reciprocal influence between parental hostility and adolescent antisocial behavior). Beyond the traditional trait-outcome approach, where, for example, aversive parental personality traits are linked to negative parenting, this framework incorporates information on both parents and offspring as well as context. Contextual factors moderate interrelationships among the three domains, particularly factors indicative of risk such as low socioeconomic status, parental history of childhood adversity, household chaos, ecological adversity, and lack of parental education.

1.2 Parental Dark Triad and Parenting

The Dark Triad is a constellation of three socially aversive personality traits – Machiavellianism, subclinical narcissism, and subclinical psychopathy (Paulhus & Williams, 2002). The central characteristics of dark traits are a lack of emotional responsiveness or

callousness and a manipulative interpersonal style (Dinić et al., 2020) which contribute to difficulties in interpersonal relationships, including parent-offspring relationships. Although they share these common characteristics, they also have unique features, and authors have recommended exploring them separately (e.g., Miller et al., 2019). Machiavellianism refers to strategic manipulation and exploitation and includes a cynical worldview; narcissism is often examined as a multidimensional trait, encompassing both grandiose (superior self-view, dominance, and high self-esteem) and vulnerable dimensions (distrust, entitlement, and low self-esteem; see Packer West et al., 2021); and psychopathy is characterized by a lack of remorse and guilt, impulsiveness, and disinhibition (Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Therefore, dark traits can show different relationships with outcomes and, in some cases, even opposite (e.g., with mental health issues, Dinić et al., 2021).

In accordance with the TDF-POTO, these variable dark trait-outcome associations also extend to parenting behavior. Extant research in Croatia ($M_{age} = 5.28$ years, Krupić et al., 2023) and Hungary ($M_{age} = 16$ years, Láng, 2018) suggests parental psychopathy and Machiavellianism are associated with harsher, controlling parenting, and additionally maternal Machiavellianism positively predicts adolescent perceptions of rejecting and overprotective parenting (Láng, 2018). The effects of parental narcissism are somewhat mixed. For example, although paternal grandiose narcissism was negatively associated with self-reported warmth, it was also associated with greater involvement in childrearing of adolescents (12–15 years old) compared to fathers of infants and toddlers (0–3 years old, Finzi-Dottan & Cohen, 2014).

However, when narcissism was conceptualized as a multidimensional construct, Truhan et al. (2022) showed that parental narcissistic neuroticism (similar to vulnerable narcissism) was negatively and narcissistic extraversion (similar to grandiose narcissism) was positively associated with paternal warmth, whereas only narcissistic antagonism (as shared core among the two narcissistic dimensions) was negatively related to maternal warmth. Paternal narcissistic extraversion had a negative effect on hostility, whereas the effect of paternal psychopathy was positive. In mothers, Machiavellianism had a strong, positive effect on hostile parenting. Extant research therefore indicates grandiose narcissistic facets exhibit associations with more adaptive parenting, whereas Machiavellianism, psychopathy, and vulnerable narcissistic facets associate with maladaptive parenting. However, according to the TDF-POTO, relationships between dark

traits and parenting also depend on contextual risk factors, which may moderate personality-parenting associations.

1.3 Parental Dark Triad and Parenting: Moderating Role of Contextual Factors

Consistent with the TDF-POTO, we explore parents' past adverse childhood experiences occurring before age 18 years (ACEs: neglect, abuse, household dysfunction), and current socioeconomic status (SES) as indicators of risk factors tied to context. Parental history of ACEs is positively associated with maladaptive parenting behavior (Lotto et al., 2023) and negatively related to quality of parent-child interactions (Weistra et al., 2024). Low SES can lead to more negative parenting through greater parental distress, lower access to resources, and a lack of knowledge and expectations (Roubinov & Boyce, 2017). Meta-analytic evidence indicates childhood SES may interact with personality to predict important life outcomes, including educational attainment and future SES (Ayoub et al., 2018). Personality has effects on individuals' responses to stress (Luo et al., 2023), and may therefore play an important role in how individuals parent their children after exposure to adversity in their own childhood, as well as in difficult environments (i.e., low SES).

Earlier research found ecological adversity (sum of sociodemographic risk factors and life stress) moderated Big Five personality-parenting associations for mothers of toddlers ($M_{age} = 2.53$ years), such that agreeableness was associated with positive parenting only in contexts of low ecological adversity (Kochanska et al., 2012). In the UK, maternal extraversion was positively associated with parental control of adolescents ($M_{age} = 13.85$ years) in high SES households, whereas the opposite was true in low SES households (Truhan et al., 2022). Further, there was a negative relationship between paternal Machiavellianism and warmth only at *low* levels of past ACEs, but not at high levels. Therefore, harsher environments characterized by greater history of ACEs or low SES may either suppress typically positive effects of parental personality, or exacerbate the effects of maladaptive traits. Other than the aforementioned studies, there is a relative lack of research which has systematically examined the interaction of dark traits with contextual risk factors to influence parenting. The current study will address this gap, providing important insight into personality, context, and their collective impact on family functioning in Serbia, a relatively understudied culture.

1.4 Parental Dark Triad, Parenting and Offspring Behavioral Outcomes

Beyond the effects of parental dark traits on parenting, these traits also impact adolescent outcomes. As shown in the TDF-POTO, effects of parental traits on offspring do not occur in isolation, but rather in concert with parenting behavior and context, and as such it is necessary to consider all domains. While parental hostility and warmth are generally considered maladaptive and adaptive forms of parenting behavior, respectively, control may have both negative and positive attributes. Control refers to the attempts made by parents to regulate, manipulate, or manage their children's behavior (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005). Control that is authoritative in nature, setting fair limits but still supporting adolescent autonomy, is positive for adolescent development, whereas control that is more coercive in nature contributes to deleterious adolescent outcomes such as increased anxiety (Van Der Bruggen et al., 2008). A recent study showed parental rejection, punishment, and control were positively linked to violence propensity among adolescents (11–18 years old), while parental warmth was negatively associated (Yendell et al., 2022).

In testing these postulations from the TDF-POTO, in a model with parental dark traits and parenting, only psychopathy negatively predicted adolescent prosocial behavior (Truhan et al., 2022). In addition, Truhan et al. (2022) found positive effects of parental hostility on adolescent externalizing and internalizing behaviors, and negative effects on prosocial behaviors, but these effects did not pass the correction for multiple comparisons. Later, Truhan et al. (2023) found adolescents who perceived a lack of paternal warmth reported higher internalizing behaviors. Other research (Vignando & Bizumic, 2022) showed higher paternal grandiose narcissism had a direct effect on anxiety and depression in emerging adults ($M_{age} = 22.38$), whereas maternal and paternal vulnerable narcissism, and maternal grandiose narcissism had indirect effects on anxiety and depression via scapegoating. Similarly, parental narcissism was related to depression and anxiety in emerging adults ($M_{age} = 22.85$), but this relationship was fully mediated by rearing behaviors as recalled by the offspring (Dentale et al., 2015). In Lau et al.'s (2024) study, parental narcissism and Machiavellianism were positively correlated with both internalizing and externalizing issues in their emerging adult offspring ($M_{age} = 19.05$), while parental psychopathy was positively correlated with externalizing issues. However, this recent study did not operationalize narcissism multidimensionally and did not consider the impact of parenting behaviors on offspring outcomes.

1.5 The Current Study

The aim of this study is to test the TDF-POTO of interconnected parental and contextual factors on parenting behavior, and, in turn, adolescent offspring behavioral outcomes (Truhan et al., 2024) in the new ground of the more traditional cultural context of Serbia. First, we attempt to replicate previous findings regarding the relationships between parental dark traits and parenting, including investigation of the moderating role of contextual risk factors (low SES and high ACEs) and extend them to the context of the Serbian culture. Although previous research showed some unique relationships between parental dark traits and parenting (e.g., Krupić et al., 2023; Láng, 2018) as well as nonsignificant relationships with some parenting behaviors (e.g., with control, see Truhan et al., 2022), we generally expect parental dark traits to be positively associated with negative parenting (e.g., hostility) and negatively with positive parenting (e.g., warmth) (**H1**). Considering the multidimensionality of narcissism and its adaptive (grandiose) and maladaptive aspects (both grandiose and vulnerable, see Dinić & Vujić, 2019), we expect to find higher levels of negative parenting and lower levels of positive parenting associated with vulnerable narcissism, and the opposite pattern for grandiose narcissism. Furthermore, we expect stronger positive associations between dark traits and negative parenting, as well as stronger negative associations between dark traits and positive parenting in the presence of risk factors (**H2**), although this is a relatively understudied area so these predictions remain exploratory.

Second, we explore the effects of parental dark traits and both self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting on adolescent behavioral outcomes. In line with previous research (e.g., Dentale et al., 2015; Truhan et al., 2022), we expect higher parental dark traits and negative parenting will be associated with problematic behavior in offspring (**H3**). Considering the inconsistent results regarding narcissism, we also explored separate effects of vulnerable and grandiose narcissism.

The study was preregistered (<https://osf.io/8vjct/>) and among preregistered hypotheses, H1, H2, and H4 were tested (H1, H2, and H3 in this study, respectively).

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants and Procedure

The sample included 239 parent-adolescent dyads from Serbia (478 participants in total), all White. Parents (68.6% mothers) had a mean age of 44.68 years ($SD = 6.16$, range 27-63) and 14.6% were single parents. The majority (56.1%) finished elementary or high school, and 29.3%

had a faculty degree. Adolescents (61.1% daughters) had an average age of 14.11 years ($SD = 2.23$, range 11-17). Power analyses using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2009) indicated our sample had 80% power to detect small interaction effects ($f^2 > .033$) and over 99% power to detect medium interaction effects ($f^2 = .15$). The majority of data were collected by trained students as part of their pre-exam activities. Each student collected data from two dyads (with adolescents aged 11-17 years) in person. Participants were persons from students' social networks, e.g., family friends and acquaintances. Since students are from the whole territory of Serbia, we assume that participants were also from the same places although we did not collect this information. The other part of the data was obtained via high schools in several cities in Vojvodina, Serbia. In this case, adolescents filled out measures in class, and their parents at a parent-teacher meetings. All measures were administered in paper-and-pencil form with informed consent and written debriefing provided to both parents and adolescents. The study was approved by the [anonymized]. Data were collected in 2024.

2.2 Measures

2.2.1 Parental Self-Reported Measures

Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (DTDD; Jonason & Webster, 2010, for Serbian adaptation and psychometric characteristics see Dinić et al., 2018) consists of 12 items with a 5-point scale (1 = *disagree strongly*, 5 = *agree strongly*), but for the purpose of this study only psychopathy (4 items) and Machiavellianism (4 items) scales were used, and narcissism was assessed via a separate multidimensional measure. Descriptive statistics and omegas (reliability) for all measures in this study are presented in Table 1 and items can be seen at <https://osf.io/uhkb7>.

Five Factor Narcissism Inventory - Super-Short Form (FFNI-SSF; Packer West et al., 2021, for Serbian adaptation and psychometric characteristics see Dinić et al., 2022) consists of 15 items with a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *disagree strongly*, 5 = *agree strongly*) and measures grandiose (11 items, $Range = 11-55$) and vulnerable (4 items, $Range = 4-20$) narcissism.

Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire/Control-Short Form (PARQ/Control Short Form; Rohner & Khaleque, 2005) consists of 29 items with a 4-point scale (1 = *almost never true*, 4 = *almost always true*) and measures warmth/affection (8 items, $Range = 8-32$), hostility/aggression (6 items, $Range = 6-24$), and (behavioral) control (5 items, $Range = 5-20$), referring to strictness. The Serbian adaptation was made by the first author for the purpose of this study and original meaning was checked with the author of the questionnaire.

Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaire (ACE-Q; Felitti et al., 1998, for Serbian adaptation and psychometric characteristics see Paunović et al., 2015) consists of 10 True/False items (as a checklist) that identifies experiences of abuse and neglect which occurred prior to the age of 18 years.

SES comprised other factors beyond income and education (e.g., Kochanska et al., 2012) and was calculated as a total score of: 1) self and partner income (1 = unemployed, 2 = below 40000 RSD/342 EUR, 3 = 40000-60000 RSD/342-513 EUR, 4 = 60000-80000 RSD/513-684 EUR, 5 = above 80000 RSD/684 EUR), 2) age at birth of the first child (0 = 19 years or younger, 1 = 20-22 years, 2 = 23-25 years, 3 = 26 years and older), 3) education (1 = finished elementary or high school, 2 = finished colleague, 3 = student at the faculty, 4 = finished BSc or MSc, 5 = finished postgraduate studies, magisterium, specialist studies or PhD), and 4) single parent status (0 = yes, 1 = no).

2.2.2 Adolescent-Reports on Parents

Adolescents evaluated the parenting of the parent in the dyad via the PARQ/Control Short Form, with each statement begins with “My Mother/My Father”.

2.2.3 Adolescents' Self-Reported Measures

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ; Goodman, 1998, for Serbian adaptation see official Youthinmind site <https://www.sdqinfo.org/py/sdqinfo/b3.py?language=Serbian> while for psychometric characteristics see e.g., Hrnčić & Džamonja Ignjatović, 2010) consists of 25 items with a 3-point scale (0 = *not true*, 1 = *somewhat true*, 2 = *certainly true*) and measures internalizing problems (10 items, emotional and peer problems), externalizing problems (10 items, conduct problems and hyperactivity), and prosocial behaviors (5 items).

Higher scores for all measures indicate higher presence of the construct in question.

2.3 Data Analysis

There were at most three cases of missing data for SES; therefore, missingness at random was not checked. Due to normality violations, self-reported parental warmth and self-reported and adolescent-reported parental hostility were transformed using rankit's formula. Multicollinearity between predictors was checked (all VIF < 2). Discriminant validity among the dark traits was tested using the CI_{CFA}(.9) technique (Rönkkö & Cho, 2022), or checking the 95% CI upper-limits of predictor correlations (i.e., dark trait) against the criteria of: upper limit ≥ 1 (severe problem), $0.90 \leq$ upper limit ≤ 1 (moderate problem), and $0.80 \leq$ upper limit ≤ 0.90 (marginal problem).

Finally, we estimated two path models using maximum likelihood with robust standard errors, using R package *lavaan* (Rosseel, 2012). All variables were treated as observed or manifest. Parent and adolescent age and sex were included in the models if they showed significant effects on any outcomes or endogenous variables. Standardized path β coefficients are presented in the figures, and we included only significant paths to aid interpretability.

In *Model 1* (Figure 1), parent and adolescent age and sex, parental dark traits, contextual variables (SES and parental ACEs), and dark trait-context interactions were included as predictors or exogenous variables and self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting were endogenous or outcome variables. Interaction effects were further tested using regressions and ANOVAs. The Johnson-Neyman interval (Johnson & Neyman, 1936) was used to identify the cut-off points of the moderator at which the association between the predictor and outcome variable became significant. In *Model 2* (Figure 4), adolescent age and sex, parental dark traits, and self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting were included as exogenous variables, and adolescent self-reported behavioral outcomes were endogenous variables.

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1 and correlations in Table 2. To aid in comparisons between this Serbian and UK samples, descriptive statistics from the PaCT project which was aimed to test the TDF-POTO in the UK are included in Table 1. UK and Serbian samples were similar in age ($p = .15$), but the Serbian sample comprised more female parents ($\chi^2(1) = 22.47, p < .001$) and adolescents ($\chi^2(1) = 8.57, p = .003$, see Supplement S1 for other variables).

3.2 Model 1: Effects of Parental Dark Traits and Context on Parenting Behaviors

Model 1 (Figure 1) explained 16.1%, 16.6% and 13.1% of the variance of self-reported parental warmth, hostility and control, respectively. Regarding adolescent-reported parenting, Model 1 explained 9.7%, 7.7% and 13.4% of parental warmth, hostility and control, respectively. Mothers reported higher parental warmth than fathers. Older adolescents reported lower parental warmth and parental control. Parents from higher SES households self-reported lower parental control. Parental ACEs had no effect on parenting directly, but did interact with parental vulnerable narcissism. In line with **H1**, parental psychopathy was negatively associated with self-reported parental warmth. Parental Machiavellianism was positively associated with self-reported parental

hostility and adolescent-reported parental control. Parental grandiose narcissism was negatively associated with self-reported parental control, whereas parental vulnerable narcissism was positively and negatively associated with self-reported hostility and warmth, respectively.

In line with **H2**, two significant interaction effects were identified. The first was an ACEs x vulnerable narcissism interaction (see Figure 2). Parental vulnerable narcissism was positively associated with self-reported parental hostility only when parents had experienced two or less ACEs. The second was a SES x vulnerable narcissism interaction (see Figure 3). Parental vulnerable narcissism was positively associated with adolescent-reported parental hostility only in low SES households (≤ 10). Correlations between parent self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting were moderate (Table 2). Differences between self-reports and adolescent-reports on parenting were significant for warmth [$t(476) = 4.00, p < .001$] and control [$t(476) = 4.93, p < .001$] with parents reporting higher scores.

3.3 Model 2: Effects of Parental Dark Traits and Parenting on Adolescent Behavioral Outcomes

Model 2 (Figure 4) explained 17.9%, 14.8% and 17.7% of self-reported adolescent externalizing, internalizing and prosocial behaviors, respectively. Adolescent females reported higher levels of internalizing and prosocial behavior. In line with **H3**, parental Machiavellianism was negatively associated with adolescent prosocial behavior. Self-reported parental warmth was positively associated with adolescent internalizing behavior. Adolescent-reported parental hostility was positively associated with externalizing and internalizing behavior, and negatively with prosocial behavior. Adolescent-reported parental control was negatively associated with externalizing behavior.

3.4 Alternate Models

The CI upper-limit passed the cut-off of .90 for the correlation between Machiavellianism and grandiose narcissism (.93) and grandiose and vulnerable narcissism (.91), indicating potential discriminant validity problems. Therefore, alternate path models were estimated to check significance of effects, with grandiose narcissism removed and then with Machiavellianism removed (see Supplement S2). All effects remained, except that Machiavellianism and adolescent-reported control became marginally significant ($\beta = .15, p = .06$).

4 Discussion

This research tested the Tri-Directional Framework of Parent and Offspring Traits and Outcomes (Truhan et al., 2024) in the new ground of the Serbian culture. Findings from the UK were replicated regarding the association between vulnerable narcissism and self-reported warmth and hostility, as well as the positive association between Machiavellianism and hostility (which was found in mothers in the UK; Truhan et al., 2022). Some similarities were observed with subtle differences, such that Serbian parental Machiavellianism was negatively associated with adolescent prosocial behavior (whereas in UK, adolescent Machiavellianism showed this pattern); Serbian adolescent-reported parental hostility was positively associated with adolescent internalizing and externalizing behavior, and negatively with prosocial behavior, which was mirrored by UK self-reported parental hostility. Interestingly, there was an opposite effect of adolescent-reported warmth between the two samples – Serbian adolescent-reported warmth was positively associated with internalizing problems, whereas in the UK it was negative. Overall, however, there were distinct differences in how dark traits related to parenting, context, and adolescent behavioral outcomes. It is also important to consider the Serbian sample comprised majority female adolescents and parents and reported a lower SES than the UK sample, which may have contributed to some of the observed differences.

Results confirmed **H1** as Machiavellianism and vulnerable narcissism were positively associated with self-reported hostility and adolescent-reported control (Machiavellianism only), while psychopathy and vulnerable narcissism were negatively associated with warmth. In contrast, grandiose narcissism was only negatively related to self-reported control. Thus, psychopathy is more associated with a lack of positive emotions and investment in relationships with children, which is in line with research indicating lack of empathy as the central characteristic of psychopathy (e.g., Verschuere et al., 2018). Parents high in Machiavellianism and vulnerable narcissism may use more physical and verbal aggressive behaviors, in line with the UK study (Truhan et al., 2022). Contrarily, grandiose narcissism was associated with a lack of self-reported parental behavioral control, which was not found in the UK study. In Serbia, self-centered and self-absorbed parents may therefore pay less attention to their adolescent offspring's behavior, or perhaps they may feel confident in their parenting approach, believing they are fostering their offspring's autonomous decisions and see no need to regulate their behavior. We should note that control in the PARQ/Control is defined as behavioral control, which includes insisting on

following strict rules, imposing desired behavior, and monitoring it. In a systematic review (González-Cámara et al., 2019), parental control measured by the PARQ/Control was characterized as extreme behavioral control (e.g., excessive or overly strict control), which is likely detrimental, although this effect depends on the particular outcome in question.

There are some distinctions regarding the source of parenting reports - self-report or adolescent-report. Although effects of all dark traits were obtained on self-reported parenting, Machiavellianism showed an additional positive effect on adolescent-reported parental control, although this effect became marginally significant in alternate models. Since the main characteristic of Machiavellianism is a tendency towards manipulation, this tendency may include their children. A lack of autonomy support and increased controlling behavior towards children by Machiavellian parents could be seen as a tactic to ensure the adolescent's behavior will not damage the parents' and family's reputation. This result is in line with Láng (2018), showing the positive effect of maternal Machiavellianism on adolescents' perception of overprotective parenting in Hungarian families. During adolescence, with increased need for independence and autonomy (Assor, 2018), high parental behavioral control may undermine healthy socioemotional development (Van Der Bruggen et al., 2008).

Among dark traits, only the effect of vulnerable narcissism on parenting was dependent on contextual factors. One possible explanation is that contextual factors are most influential to vulnerable narcissism in terms of the parent-offspring relationship, considering this trait is strongly related to seeking excessive praise and attention from others to boost fragile self-esteem (e.g., Dinić et al., 2022). In addition, it seems adolescent perception of parenting is more shaped by shared family environment (SES) and parental perception by personal experience (ACEs). The expected positive relationship between vulnerable narcissism and adolescent-reported parental hostility was found only in low SES households, supporting **H2**. Therefore, the link between negative parenting and vulnerable narcissism appears more evident in an environment with less social and economic resources, in which satisfaction of the need for admiration may be harder to achieve, especially if social status is gained via possession of material means. This result strongly supports the central characteristic of contingent self-esteem in vulnerable narcissism, which refers to the instability of self-esteem dependent on external sources (Dinić et al., 2022).

However, parents who are low in vulnerable narcissism, exhibiting a surety in self and trust in their relationships, expressed a lack of hostility in contexts characterized by little past adversity,

which is not in line with **H2**. When parents experienced greater past adversity, they reported higher hostility no matter their level of vulnerable narcissism. Therefore, in the presence of high ACEs, other factors may shape parenting, like stress response and regulation (e.g., Steele et al., 2016). Truhan et al. (2022) also found a similar moderation trend in the relationship between Machiavellianism and paternal warmth. We should note that most of the parents had none (46.4%) or had only one ACE (22.6%), which could affect the results.

Finally, in testing **H3**, only parental Machiavellianism was negatively associated with adolescent prosocial behavior, which remained significant in alternate models. Although the effects of other dark traits were expected, it seems parental Machiavellianism is the key dark trait related to adolescent behavioral outcomes, in particular prosociality, in a Serbian sample. In the UK, only parental psychopathy had a negative effect on adolescents' prosocial behavior, but this effect did not pass the *p*-correction (Truhan et al., 2022). Our results support modeling/identification hypotheses by which children acquire the ideology and associated skills which their parents have used to manipulate and exploit others, including themselves (e.g., Kraut & Price, 1976).

Furthermore, among parenting dimensions, self-reported parental warmth was positively associated with adolescent internalizing behavior, which was not expected. There are several explanations for this result. Adolescents whose primary socialization figures are still parents, and not peers, may tend to feel lonelier in peer groups and prefer spending time with parents compared to peers. In line with the mutual dynamic between parents and offspring (Truhan et al., 2024), adolescents who internalize more may seek more attention and support from parents, who, in turn, respond to and reinforce these needs. This could be specific to more traditional and collectivistic cultures, such as Serbian, which emphasize the importance of family interests, as opposed to individualistic interests and development (Mihic & Petrovic, 2009). Regarding adolescent-reported parenting, parental hostility was associated with all dimensions of adolescent behavioral outcomes, in the expected direction, and parental control was negatively associated with externalizing behavior. The last result aligns with previous studies (see González-Cámara et al., 2019 for a review), where adolescent-reported parental control (measured by the PARQ/Control) is linked to negative emotional outcomes (mainly self-esteem), while externalizing behaviors like substance use and problematic behavior often show either a non-significant or opposite association with perceived control, as in our study. This effect is not related to the cultural context (González-

Cámara et al., 2019). Taken together, results mainly support **H3**, except for the relationship between parental warmth and internalizing behavior.

Finally, we should note the differences between parent self-reports and adolescent-reports on parenting, with parents presenting themselves as more positive. These differences may be due to perception discrepancies, i.e., parents might perceive their actions as authoritative or nurturing, while adolescents may interpret them differently, especially if they are experiencing conflict or emotional distress. Additionally, self-reports can be biased by social desirability, compared to other-reports.

There are several limitations of this study. First, scores on some scales had lower reliability, e.g., adolescent-reported parental control and vulnerable narcissism. Therefore, the results linked to these scales should be taken with caution. Second, due to the self-report method, social desirability and biased self-image cannot be ruled out (Tamborski et al., 2012). Future studies might include observational measures of parenting. Third, due to gender disbalance and modest sample size, we did not investigate mothers' and fathers' effects, although parental sex was included as a control variable. This was also different to the PaCT project, which comprised a balanced sample of both parent and adolescent males and females. Future studies should include self-report and adolescent-report for both parents. Fourth, considering some differences in the characteristics of samples from the UK and Serbia, a direct comparison of the results would not be appropriate. However, González-Cámara et al. (2019) concluded that results regarding the relationships between parenting and offspring outcomes may not necessarily depend on the culture/country, but on the used instrument. Since we used the same instruments as in the PaCT project, we can make some meaningful comparisons, although indirect, keeping in mind the differences between the samples. Fifth, due to many predictors in the models and the modest sample size, some results could be false positive (although we utilized robust estimation techniques). True interaction effects could be difficult to detect, particularly the very small interaction effect of vulnerable narcissism and SES ($f^2 = .023$). Finally, considering the cross-sectional design, we cannot assume causal relationships. Previous longitudinal research in Croatia has shown bidirectional dynamics between parental and offspring characteristics (Ručević et al., 2023). In addition, while we set contextual factors as moderators in line with the TDF-POTO, they can be considered as predictors and affect parenting (for ACEs see Lotto et al., 2023 and Weistra et al., 2024; for SES see Roubinov & Boyce, 2017). Therefore, future research might consider a

longitudinal design to test which direction of relationships is more likely, and use of multilevel modeling to distinguish between- and within-country differences and to test true contextual effects.

4.1 Conclusion

In sum, results mainly confirmed hypotheses from the TDF-POTO in Serbian culture. Parental personality plays an important role within the parent-offspring relationship, particularly regarding both parent and adolescent-reported parenting behavior. Furthermore, significant vulnerable narcissism-context interactions emerged, implying research should consider contextual factors to fully grasp the effect of personality on parenting and offspring development. It could be seen that some relationships between dark traits and parenting, and between parenting and adolescent behavioral outcomes appear culturally-specific (e.g., warmth-internalizing symptoms). Thus, the study provides new insights into the parent-offspring relationship, highlighting the need to move past ‘generalizability’ towards more culturally-specific parental practices. The practical implications of these findings highlight the importance of educating parents on creating a family environment that fosters adolescents’ autonomy development while ensuring their boundaries are respected. In the cultural context of Serbia, this practice may be particularly challenging due to traditionally close parent-child relationships and prevailing parenting that may emphasize control over fostering autonomy. Therefore, tailored interventions that consider these cultural nuances are essential, focusing on balancing parental warmth and guidance with strategies that promote healthy autonomy development in adolescents.

Preregistration

The study was preregistered at <https://osf.io/>.

Author Contributions

Bojana M. Dinić: conceptualization, data curation, investigation, writing – original draft, writing - review and editing. Lauren M. Ferguson: data curation, visualization, formal analysis, writing – review and editing. Kostas A. Papageorgiou: writing – review and editing. Tayler E. Truhan: conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, writing – review and editing.

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Ethics Statement

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Figure 1. Path analysis of Model 1 - prediction of self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting based on parent and adolescent sex and age, parental dark traits, context (SES and parental ACEs), and their interaction.

Note: C = child report. Only significant predictors, paths, and interaction terms are included. Standardized path coefficients are reported. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Figure 2. Parental adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) moderate the association between parental vulnerable narcissism and self-reported parental hostility, $F(3,233) = 9.02, p < .001, R^2 = 0.10$; $\Delta F(1,233) = 8.24, \Delta p < .004; f^2 = .035$. Parental vulnerable narcissism was positively associated with self-reported parental hostility when parents had experienced two or less ACEs ($\beta = .32, SE = 0.08, p < .001$). For parents with three or more ACEs, there was no significant association between parental vulnerable narcissism and self-reported parental hostility ($\beta = .07, SE = 0.11, p = .56$).

Figure 3. Socioeconomic status (SES) moderates the association between parental vulnerable narcissism and adolescent-reported parental hostility, $F(3,232) = 3.11, p < .027, R^2 = 0.04$; $\Delta F(1,232) = 5.43, \Delta p < .02; f^2 = .023$. In low SES households (≤ 10), parental vulnerable narcissism was positively associated with adolescent-reported parental hostility ($\beta = .29, SE = 0.10, p < .003$). However, in high SES households (> 11), parental vulnerable narcissism was not significantly associated with adolescent-reported parental hostility ($\beta = -.06, SE = 0.12, p = .61$).

Figure 4. Path analysis of Model 2 - prediction of adolescent behavioral outcomes based on adolescent sex and age (parent sex and age were not significant), parental dark traits, and parent self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting.

Note: Only significant predictors and paths are included. Standardized path coefficients are reported. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Reliability for scales included in the current study and the comparison PaCT study in the UK

Serbia									United Kingdom								
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Var	Rge	Kur	Skw	<i>I</i> (<i>n</i>)	ω	α		<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Var	Rge	Kur	Skw	<i>I</i> (<i>n</i>)	ω	α
Adolescents (<i>N</i> = 239)									Adolescents (<i>N</i> = 310)								
A.Age	14.11 (2.23)	4.95	6.00	-	-	-	-	-	A.Age	13.85 (1.97)	3.88	6.00	-	-	-	-	-
A.Sex	61.1% F	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	A.Sex	48.7% F	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.WMT	28.57 (4.07)	16.56	19.00	3.07	-1.71	8	.82	.65	A.WMT	28.26 (3.40)	11.58	17.00	0.82	-1.05	8	.87	.86
A.HOST	7.84 (2.55)	6.49	18.00	8.13	2.37	6	.76	.60	A.HOST	7.14 (1.59)	2.52	8.00	2.91	1.73	6	.72	.71
A.CONT	13.61 (2.70)	7.27	15.00	0.35	-0.18	5	.54	.59	A.CONT	12.96 (2.64)	6.95	12.50	-0.41	-0.05	5	.71	.68
INT	4.96 (3.32)	11.04	15.00	-0.14	0.67	10	.71	.70	INT	5.47 (3.45)	11.93	16.00	0.02	0.68	10	.74	.73
EXT	5.38 (3.14)	9.87	16.00	0.22	0.75	10	.70	.69	EXT	6.24 (3.92)	15.39	17.00	-0.43	0.45	10	.80	.79
PRO	8.41 (1.80)	3.25	8.00	1.36	-1.36	5	.73	.71	PRO	7.60 (1.95)	3.80	10.00	0.26	-0.73	5	.74	.74
Parents (<i>N</i> = 239)									Parents (<i>N</i> = 283)								
P.Age	44.68 (6.16)	37.91	36.00	-	-	-	-	-	P.Age	45.86 (6.71)	45.02	35.00	-	-	-	-	-
P.Sex	68.9% F	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	P.Sex	46.9% F	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SES	12.51 (3.76)	14.13	17.00	-0.43	-0.28	5	.62	.58	SES	17.89 (4.42)	19.50	21.00	-0.64	-0.03	5	.57	.49
ACEs	1.14 (1.50)	2.25	8.00	2.84	1.65	10	.64	.64	ACEs	1.45 (2.12)	4.49	10.00	3.60	1.92	10	.84	.84
MAC	1.51 (0.64)	0.40	3.25	3.01	1.63	4	.83	.82	MAC	1.94 (0.81)	0.65	3.50	-0.43	0.60	4	.78	.78
PSY	1.58 (0.59)	0.35	2.75	0.90	1.10	4	.67	.66	PSY	1.84 (0.81)	0.65	3.75	1.16	1.15	4	.85	.84
G.NAR	2.29 (0.53)	0.28	2.83	0.28	0.24	11	.75	.74	G.NAR	2.22 (0.54)	0.30	3.45	0.70	0.52	11	.74	.73
V.NAR	2.41 (0.78)	0.49	3.67	-0.17	0.19	4	.55	.55	V.NAR	2.48 (0.74)	0.55	3.50	-0.55	0.32	4	.59	.58
P.WMT	30.58 (2.17)	4.69	13.00	8.02	-2.49	8	.68	.81	P.WMT	30.15 (2.37)	5.61	11.00	-1.43	-0.22	8	.78	.78
P.HOST	7.55 (2.00)	4.01	15.00	9.02	2.27	6	.63	.74	P.HOST	7.59 (1.94)	3.78	10.00	-1.44	0.23	6	.68	.66
P.CONT	14.79 (2.55)	6.53	13.00	-0.14	-0.15	5	.62	.53	P.CONT	14.24 (2.17)	4.70	13.00	0.56	-0.47	5	.52	.49

Note. Values for parents and adolescents from the United Kingdom were obtained from the PaCT dataset (Truhan et al., 2022, 2023). Adolescents reported on both maternal and paternal parenting separately in PaCT; thus, values were added together and averaged to obtain general perceived parenting scores. Var = Variance, Rge = Range, Kur = Kurtosis, Skw = Skew, *I* (*n*) = Number of items, ω = McDonald's omega (1999). Adolescent variables: A.WMT = adolescent-reported parental warmth, A.HOST = adolescent-reported parental hostility, A.CONT = adolescent-reported parental control, INT = adolescent internalizing behaviors, EXT = adolescent externalizing behaviors, PRO = adolescent prosocial behaviors. Parent Variables: SES = socioeconomic status, ACEs = adverse childhood experiences, MAC = Machiavellianism, PSY = psychopathy, G.NAR = grandiose narcissism, V.NAR = vulnerable narcissism, P.WMT = self-reported parental warmth, P.HOST = self-reported parental hostility, P.CONT = self-reported parental control. Bolded means refer to significantly higher or lower scores in comparison of two samples.

Table 2

Correlations Among Variables

	SES	ACEs	MAC	PSY	G.NAR	V.NAR	P.WMT	P.HOST	P.CONT	A.WMT	A.HOST	A.CONT	INTERN	EXTERN
ACEs	-.14*													
MAC	.03	.18**												
PSY	-.02	.17**	.51***											
G.NAR	.00	.23***	.55***	.39***										
V.NAR	-.06	.26***	.31***	.13*	.41***									
P.WMT	-.03	-.10	-.15*	-.28***	-.13*	-.16*								
P.HOST	-.05	.11	.27***	.23***	.20**	.24***	-.49***							
P.CONT	-.17**	-.06	-.02	-.02	-.11	.04	.19**	.08						
A.WMT	-.01	-.09	.00	-.10	-.06	-.03	.25***	-.14*	.13*					
A.HOST	-.04	.14*	.03	.08	.04	.09	-.15*	.22***	.00	-.40***				
A.CONT	-.03	-.04	.10	.04	-.03	.03	.02	.13*	.41***	.12	.08			
INTERN	-.05	.12	.00	.09	.04	.08	.01	.07	-.05	-.21**	.26***	-.02		
EXTERN	-.05	.12	.16*	.14*	.20**	.13*	-.18**	.21***	-.10	-.13*	.35***	-.11	.38***	
PROSOC	-.08	.01	-.19**	-.10	-.09	-.03	.15*	-.13	.07	.23***	-.29***	.05	-.21***	-.43***

Note. Parent Variables: SES = socioeconomic status, ACEs = adverse childhood experiences, MAC = Machiavellianism, PSY = psychopathy, G.NAR = grandiose narcissism, V.NAR = vulnerable narcissism, P.WMT = self-reported parental warmth, P.HOST = self-reported parental hostility, P.CONT = self-reported parental control. Adolescent Variables: A.WMT = adolescent-reported parental warmth, A.HOST = adolescent-reported parental hostility, A.CONT = adolescent-reported parental control, INT = adolescent internalizing behaviors, EXT = adolescent externalizing behaviors, PRO = adolescent prosocial behaviors. Shaded cells refer to correlations between self-reported and adolescent-reported parenting. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Supplement

S1. Descriptive Statistics – Serbian and UK sample differences

Serbian adolescents perceived their parents as more hostile and controlling, while parents perceived their own parenting as warmer and more controlling compared to UK participants (Table 1). Additionally, Serbian adolescents exhibited higher prosocial and lower externalizing behavior, whereas Serbian parents reported lower SES, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy compared to UK participants.

Compared to descriptive data from previous research in Serbia on a sample with an average age of 28.13 years (Study 3 in Dinić et al., 2018) and a sample with an average age of 38.51 years (Čekrlija et al., 2023), the scores in the current sample of parents showed somewhat lower values on the Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (DTDD) scales—Machiavellianism and psychopathy. Notably, the scores in the older sample (Čekrlija et al., 2023) were lower compared to the younger sample (Dinić et al., 2018). In the UK, one study has used the Dark Triad Dirty Dozen with younger adults (mean age = 20 years), who self-reported slightly higher scores on all three traits than in the PaCT sample of parents (Jonason et al., 2020). It should be noted that this is only a rough and indirect comparison. Multiple studies indicate Machiavellianism and psychopathy decline throughout adulthood, whereas narcissism varies from stability to decline (Bartlett & Bartlett, 2015; Götz et al., 2020; Kawamoto et al., 2020). Thus, as the samples of parents from Serbia and the UK are somewhat older, we cannot rule out the possibility that the differences in scores are due to age rather than sample characteristics.

Regarding parenting scores, although there is no previous research using the PARQ/Control instrument in Serbia, studies have been conducted with a previous, long version of this instrument – PARQ. The results suggested that adolescents (aged 15-18 years) from the general population perceived their parents as warmer and less hostile, indifferent, and rejecting

in an undifferentiated manner (Kostić, 2014). More recent research with the Control scale including a sample of mothers (age 45-54 years) has shown that while the same trend can be observed, the scores on this scale are somewhat higher compared to scores on other scales (Mišić, 2022). A similar pattern was found in the current sample from Serbia. In addition, there has also not been a representative sample collected in the UK using the PARQ/Control. Other research in the UK with the previous, long PARQ form (Nekkebroeck et al., 2009) indicates parents of children 5 years of age tend to report themselves very highly on warmth and relatively low on hostility, similarly to the PaCT project.

S2. Alternate Models

The effect of Machiavellianism on self-reported hostility ($\beta = .18, p = .02$) remained significant, but adolescent perceived control became marginally nonsignificant ($\beta = .15, p = .06$). The effect of parental Machiavellianism on adolescent prosocial behavior remained significant ($\beta = -.23, p = .005$). Vulnerable narcissism remained significantly associated with self-reported hostility ($\beta = .17, p = .01$) and warmth ($\beta = -.18, p = .007$). The association between grandiose narcissism ($\beta = -.17, p = .03$) and self-reported control remained significant.

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